

CHARACTERIZATION, CHEMICAL MODIFICATION, AND PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF FLAX FIBER NATURAL COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Flax Fibers, Natural Fiber, Bio-composites, Thermoplastic Composites

Abstract

There has been increasing interest in the use of natural fiber reinforcements as a replacement to synthetic fibers, like glass, in composite structures, especially in the transportation sector. Significant work has been done with thermoset matrix composites which have resulted in several applications in the automotive sector. However, when natural fibers are used in thermoplastic matrixes the resultant fibers act as inexpensive fillers rather than reinforcement, due to fiber breakage during processing, for example in injection molding and twin screw compounding. Retaining a critical fiber aspect ratio for load transfer is imperative in their successful use in composites. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the process of extrusion compression molding as an alternate processing option for natural fiber reinforced, thermoplastic matrix composite. The process involves using a low shear extruder which achieves mixing and impregnation of the fibers with minimal damage to the fiber length, thus retaining the critical aspect ratio. Various chemical treatments to the fiber prior to processing are also evaluated for process ability and mechanical performance. The use of plasticator and twin screw compression molding to evaluate the impact of fibers' length on the strength of the composites are investigated.

1 Introduction

Natural fibers have been the leading alternative fillers for automotive, industrial and commercial composite components. Natural fiber are biodegradable and when used with thermoplastics resins, offer great advantages such as recyclability, light-weight, high strength to weight ratio and non toxic. However, natural fibers continue to have drawbacks such as variable fiber quality, poor binding to matrix materials, chemical modification required for improved composite adhesion, lower strength than synthetic fibers. There

are also many challenges in processing of natural fiber composites due to the low thermal degradation and fiber breakage which hinder the strength of the composites. US grown flax fiber is currently underutilized and has been shown to exhibit mechanical properties which are comparable to those of synthetic fibers on a small scale at a nonrenewable energy savings of 83%. The fine bast fibers are released from the stem by a process termed dew-retting. Mowed flax is dew-retted according to weather conditions and completed in a week, when weather is warm and moist, to months when weather is cold and dry.

Several researches [1-5] have shown that fibers subjected to chemical treatments such as alkaline, acid and addition of coupling agents to thermoplastic can improve the interfacial adhesion of the natural fibers with thermoplastic matrices. This work mainly focuses on processing of natural fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites by the extrusion-compression molding technology. This involves using low temperature and low shear rate to melt the pre-mixed flax fiber and polypropylene resin. Effect of chemical treatment (fibers) on mechanical properties of the composite was analyzed.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials

Flax fiber for this research was processed and supplied by USDA ARS Cotton Quality Research Station in Clemson, SC. The polypropylene matrix used for this research was supplied in a powder form by DOW Chemical Company.

2.2 Flax Fiber Processing

Dew-retted flax stalks were first processed through a 9-roller calender which crushes and separates shive from fiber using a series of grooved and smooth rollers. Secondly, flax stalks were processed through a top shaker that uses top mounted metal

CHARACTERIZATION, CHEMICAL MODIFICATION, AND PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF FLAX FIBER NATURAL

prongs that vibrate rapidly within a fiber mat pulled along a pinned apron, thus opening and further separating the shive. The third step in processing, the scutching wheel aggressively strokes the fibers over a feed plate and through grid bars further removing shive, opening fibers, shortening fibers, and enhancing the fibers softness. A five-roller calender was subsequently used to crush, compact, and help remove remaining shive. The final step in processing was passing the samples back through the top shaker to open and further separate the shive.

2.3 Characterization

Flax fibers with diameter ranging from 20-150 μm and length ranging from 12-127 mm (average length of 64 mm) were used for this research. In an extrusion-compression molding (ECM) technique, a low shear extruder is used to minimize the fiber length degradation that occurs during the processing stage. Since natural fibers degrade at much lower temperatures than the matrix resin, a burn-off procedure cannot be used to examine the fiber lengths. Hence in this study a thermoplastic resin (Polyvinyl Alcohol) that dissolves in water is utilized to study the fiber attrition / degradation that occur during the ECM process. Flax fibers and powdered Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) was mechanically mixed, using a drum mixer, PVA was used for the fiber length study only. Fig. 1, shows the fiber length distribution on flax fibers before and after ECM process. The fiber length ranges from 5.70-123 mm (average length of 45 mm.), a 30% reduction in the average length of flax fibers after processing. However, high aspect ratios are still maintained.

2.4 Chemical Treatment

Flax fibers were treated with 20wt% maleic acid (MA) for varying number of hours at 55°C. 20 wt% MA with respect to the weight of fibers were dissolved in warm acetone and the flax fibers were soaked in the solution. The treatments were done for 2, 4, 6 and 10 hours to allow the surface of the fibers to reach the saturation point in order to obtain maximum improvement of strength of the composite. The soaked fibers were dried in an oven before mixing it with polypropylene powder, using a mechanical drum mixer.

The IR-Spectrum analysis in Figure 2 indicates that at 3340 cm^{-1} there is high presence of hydroxyl groups in both untreated and treated flax fibers due to hydrophilic nature of natural fibers.

Fig. 2 indicates that both untreated and treated flax fibers contain the stretched C=O bonds at 1605 cm^{-1} which indicate the presence of hemicelluloses: acetyl and carboxylic and lignin: aldehyde. The strong peak observed around 1000 cm^{-1} is C-C bonds that illustrate the presence of polysaccharide which is the backbone of cellulose structure. Another stretched peak was observed around 1300-1490 cm^{-1} which indicate the stretching of C-O bonds due to the presence of ether groups in the backbone of cellulose structure.

The final fiber weight fraction on all the variants were kept constant at 20% by weight.

2.5 Extrusion Compression Molding

The pre-mixed fiber and resin powder was processed with a low shear extruded at low temperatures to minimize fiber breakage and thermal degradation. The temperature profiles in the low shear extruder were set at 160 °C, 170 °C and 177 °C for Zones 1-3 respectively. The molten material (mixture of molten resin and flax fibers - charge) was then transferred to a tool (12" x 12" matched metal tool) mounted on a hydraulic press. The press is equipped with heated platens to maintain the tool at a temperature of 100 °C. Once the molten charge was transferred the press was closed and a pressure of 3000 psi was applied for the molten material to flow and fill the cavity. The test plaque was de-molded from the tool after 2 minutes. Mechanical test samples were cut from these molded plaques for all the variants.

2.6 Mechanical Testing

Three point bend test (flexural test) were performed on the bio-composites according to ASTM D790 standard

3 Results & Discussions

Fig.3 shows the surface of untreated and treated flax fibers at different times. The untreated flax fibers shows high amount of coated layer i.e. pectin, lignin wax whereas the 2 hrs of MA treatment shows slight removal of coated layer, 4 hrs shows further removal of unwanted substances. After 10 hrs of MA treatment, decomposition of flax fibers can be seen. This results in degraded fibers' reducing the strength. The strong molecular lock between fiber and matrix can be formed from the elimination of coated layer which is seen from the strength of the 6 hrs MA treatment. The molecular locks provides a stronger bond between the fibers

CHARACTERIZATION, CHEMICAL MODIFICATION, AND PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF FLAX FIBER NATURAL

and the matrix and hence leads to higher mechanical properties of the composite

3.1 Mechanical Properties – Effect of Chemical Treatment

Fig. 4 shows the effect of the chemical treatment on the flexural properties of 20 wt% flax fiber reinforced polypropylene composites. Figure 5 show the SEM images on the fractured surface of all the variants. The flexural strengths obtained after Maleic Acid treatment were 44 MPa, 47 MPa, 55 MPa and 42 MPa and flexural modulus were 2.21 GPa, 2.29 GPa, 2.820 GPa and 1.70 GPa for 2, 4, 6 and 10 hrs respectively. The 6 hrs treatments have shown to have maximum improvement on the flexural strength and elastic modulus of the bio-composite. The increase in treatment time beyond 6 hrs has shown to degrade the fibers and hence lower the strength and modulus of the bio-composite to less than that of 4 hrs. The decrease in strength after 10 hrs of MA treatment correlate to the surface analysis shown in Fig. 3 and the fracture surface observed in Fig. 5. The reduction on the strength of the composite after 10 hrs of MA treatment is due to the reduction on the amount of cellulose as also observed on the IR-Spectrum analysis (Fig. 2).

3.2 Conclusion

The use a low shear extruder for the compression molding process minimizes the fiber length and hence maximizes the strength of the composite by maintaining the higher aspect ratios of fibers. Although critical aspect ratio of the fiber is an important factor influencing the strength of the composite, interfacial strength between the fiber and the matrix plays a major role in transferring the mechanical load from the matrix to the fiber. The chemical treatment of fibers with Maleic acid (MA) can be used to remove the unwanted waxy layer from fiber surface. This in turn helps in the formation of a chemical bond between the fiber and polypropylene matrix. A maximum of 6 hrs of MA treatment has shown to reduce the amount of waxy layer at the surface of flax fibers, and thereby improved the interfacial bond between the fiber and the matrix. Addition of 20% (w/w) of treated flax fibers to polypropylene resulted in improvements in flexural properties. Flax fibers treated with MA for 6 hrs exhibits a 150% improvement on the flexural strength and 250% improvement on the flexural modulus from that of unreinforced polypropylene. Treatment beyond 6 hours results in fiber

degradation and hence a decrease in flexural strength and modulus.

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Figures:

Fig.1. Fiber (Flax Fibers) length distribution before and after extrusion compression molding process

CHARACTERIZATION, CHEMICAL MODIFICATION, AND PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF FLAX FIBER NATURAL

Fig.2. IR spectrum analysis of untreated, 6 hrs treated and 10 hrs treated flax fibers

Fig. 5 SEM image showing the fracture surface of flax fiber composites under different fiber treatments (a & b) 4 hrs of MA treatment (c & d) 10 hrs of MA treatment

Fig.3. SEM images showing surface of flax fibers a) untreated b) 2 hrs of MA treatment c) 4 hrs of MA treatment d) 10 hrs of MA treatment.

Fig.4. Comparison of flexural strength - Effect of varying chemical treatment duration on flax fibers with maleic acid